

Clinical Anatomy of the Lumbar Spine: A Morphometric and Radiological Approach in a South Indian Population: Observational studyS. Megala¹, B. Paventhan², G. Subbulakshmi³, G. Amudha⁴¹Assistant Professor, Department of Anatomy, Government Erode Medical College, Perundurai, Tamil Nadu, India²Fellowship in perinatology, Senior Assistant Surgeon, Government Headquarters Hospital Erode, Tamilnadu, India³Professor and Head, Department of Anatomy, Government Erode Medical College, Perundurai, Tamil Nadu, India⁴Professor and Head, Department of Anatomy, PSG Institute of Medical Sciences & Research, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** This anatomical study aimed to conduct morphometric analysis of desiccated lumbar vertebrae in human cadavers.**Methods:** The study examined adult dry lumbar vertebrae bones and MRI images at PSG Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, with approval from the Institutional Ethics committee. The study lasted three years and involved anthropometric measurements of 100 vertebrae from L1 to L5 using Vernier Caliper.**Results:** The incidence of round, oval, triangle, and trefoil shapes varied across different levels of the data. No significant difference was observed between pedicle length of right and left side. Highly significant differences were observed between vertebral body anteroposterior and transverse diameters of L1 vertebrae with other vertebrae. The study found that the vertebral body's anterior length was longer at the inferior border, and lamina length was greater on the right ($p < 0.01$). Left-sided specimens had higher lamina height and other parameters.**Conclusion:** The study provided crucial anatomical dimensions for lumbar vertebrae, essential in surgical practice, enabling the manufacturing of implants based on the specific sample population.**Keywords:** Lumbar Vertebrae, Anatomy, Morphometric, Radiological study.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

The term 'lumbus' in Latin refers to a lion, therefore lumbar vertebrae are metaphorically associated with a lion. They possess a high degree of flexibility and provide stability to the vertebral column. There is a limited amount of research on the morphometric data of the lumbar vertebrae, and there are even less studies on the size of the pars inter-articularis in anatomical collections.

The pars interarticularis is situated between the superior and inferior articular facets of the zygapophyseal joints in each vertebra. The radiographs of the lumbar vertebrae show that the pars inter-articularis bears a resemblance to the neck of a Scottish dog [1].

Given that surgical procedures on the vertebral column rely on the use of certain bone landmarks, it is crucial to have accurate morphometric data for the different regions of the vertebrae. Precise understanding of the anatomical dimensions is

crucial for comprehending the causes and development of lower back pain [2-3]. The anatomical structures such as the pars inter-articularis, transverse process, and superior and inferior articular facets play a crucial role in the internal fixation of the lumbar spine.

The pars interarticularis are crucial components of the lumbar vertebrae that play a significant role in surgical instrumentation. Anatomical studies aid in comprehending the intricate morphometry of the vertebral column. There is a hypothesis that the morphometry of the vertebrae is a contributing factor to degenerative illnesses of the vertebral column.

Accurate measurements are crucial when selecting an appropriate implant to prevent the intervertebral space from exceeding its limits and causing future harm to the blood vessels. [5] The aim of this anatomical investigation was to measure the size

and shape of dried lumbar vertebrae from human cadavers in a sample group of Indians.

Aim of the Study:

The aim and objective of the study is

- To determine normal morphology and morphometric measurements of lumbar vertebrae in adult dry bones and Magnetic Resonance Imaging in Tamilnadu population.
- To find out sexual differences in the morphometric dimensions of lumbar vertebrae.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted at PSG Institute of Medical Sciences and Research following approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee. It was an observational study carried out over three years, involving both dry lumbar vertebrae bones and MRI images. The study design and sample size included 100 dry lumbar vertebrae and MRI scan images from 100 males and 100 females.

Materials were collected from the Department of Anatomy, PSG Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Coimbatore, and the Department of Radiology, PSG Hospitals. MRI images were acquired using a 1.5 Tesla MRI in T2/TSE (Turbo Spin Echo) non-contrast axial, sagittal, and coronal planes with a slice thickness of 3 mm. Various anthropometric measurements of the lumbar vertebrae from L1 to L5 were taken using a Vernier Caliper with a resolution of 0.01 mm.

Inclusion criteria were adult lumbar vertebrae without erosion or deformity and normal MRI scans without deformed vertebrae. Exclusion criteria included damaged, eroded, deformed, and anomalous vertebrae, as well as MRI scans with lumbar vertebrae fractures, vertebral abnormalities, spinal tumors, Pott's spine, Paget's disease, congenital spinal deformities, previous spinal surgery, or gross spinal pathology like spondylolisthesis.

The following parameters were measured and documented: antero-posterior diameter of the vertebral body, transverse diameter of the vertebral body,

antero-posterior diameter of the spinal canal (mid-sagittal diameter), transverse diameter of the spinal canal (interpedicular distance), canal body ratio (C/B), pedicle length, pedicle width (transverse diameter of pedicle), and pedicle height (vertical diameter of pedicle).

The morphology of the spinal canal was also recorded, with shapes including circular, oval, triangular, and trefoil.

Radiomorphometric measurements were taken from MRI images collected retrospectively for various clinical conditions from PACS (Picture Archiving Communication System) software. Only images clearly showing all bony structures were included. Parameters measured included the antero-posterior and transverse diameters of the vertebral body, antero-posterior and transverse diameters of the spinal canal (mid-sagittal diameter), and pedicle length. These measurements were taken using axial (t2-tse-tra-msma LS) and sagittal planes (t2-tse-sag) for vertebral body measurements, and axial plane (t2-spc-rst-tra-p2-LS) for spinal canal and pedicle measurements.

All recorded data were subjected to statistical analysis using SPSS software. Statistical methods included the calculation of mean, standard deviation, standard deviation error, and student's t-test. Results were evaluated within a 95% confidence interval, and significance was determined with a probability level of less than 0.05.

Results

The study examined the morphological features and measurements of adult dry lumbar vertebrae, revealing three variants: round, oval, triangular, and trefoil.

The round shape was the rarest variant, with oval shapes more common in L1 and L2 vertebrae. Triangle shapes were more common in L3 and L4, while trefoil shapes were present in L4 and L5. The incidence of round shapes was 15% in L1, 10% in L2, 85% in L1, 90% in L2, 80% in L3, 95% in L4, and 5% in L5.

Table 1: Incidence of Morphological variants in vertebral canal of adult dry lumbar vertebrae

Vertebra	No of Vertebra	Shapes of Vertebrae							
		Round Shaped		Oval Shaped		Triangle Shaped		Trefoil Shaped	
		NO	Incidence	No	Incidence	No	Incidence	No	Incidence
L1	20	3	15%	17	85%	NIL	0%	NIL	0%
L2	20	2	10%	18	90%	NIL	0%	NIL	0%
L3	20	NIL	0%	4	20%	16	80%	NIL	0%
L4	20	NIL	0%	NIL	0%	19	95%	1	5%
L5	20	NIL	0%	NIL	0%	7	35%	13	65%

The table 1 observed the shapes of lumbar vertebrae (L1 to L5) in a sample of 20 vertebrae each. The findings revealed that the L1 vertebrae were predominantly oval-shaped (85%), with a smaller pro-

portion being round-shaped (15%). Similarly, L2 vertebrae were mainly oval-shaped (90%) with 10% being round-shaped. The L3 vertebrae showed a different pattern, with 80% being triangle-shaped

and 20% oval-shaped. For L4, the majority were triangle-shaped (95%) with a small proportion being trefoil-shaped (5%). Lastly, L5 vertebrae were predominantly trefoil-shaped (65%) with 35% being triangle-shaped. This

indicates a variation in the shapes of vertebrae along the lumbar spine, with oval shapes being more common in the upper lumbar vertebrae and triangle and trefoil shapes more common in the lower lumbar vertebrae.

Figure 1: Comparisons of morphological variants in vertebral canal among the lumbar vertebrae

The study found significant differences in the anteroposterior and transverse diameters of vertebral bodies and spinal canals across lumbar levels (L1 to L5) using MRI images from 200 patients. L1 and L2 vertebrae were predominantly oval-shaped, L3 and L4 were mostly triangular, and L5 had a mix of triangular and trefoil shapes. Specifically, 95% of

L1 vertebrae in males and 90% in females were oval-shaped, while 90% of L3 vertebrae in males and 95% in females were triangular. L5 had 50% triangular and 60% trefoil shapes in males and females, respectively. These findings underscore the variability in vertebral dimensions and shapes along the lumbar spine.

Table 2: Comparison of anteroposterior diameter of vertebral body in both male and female

Vertebral Dimension	Vertebral level	Male		Female		t-test
		Mean	Std deviation	Mean	Std deviation	
Vertebral body anteroposterior diameter	L1	27.89	0.87	26.93	0.88	0.00**
	L2	30.29	0.91	29.65	0.90	0.03*
	L3	32.20	1.18	31.59	1.21	0.11
	L4	35.35	0.85	34.78	0.90	0.04*
	L5	37.04	0.86	36.46	0.77	0.03*

The table 2 the study compared the vertebral body anteroposterior diameters between male and female lumbar vertebrae (L1 to L5) and found significant differences at several levels.

For L1, males had a mean diameter of 27.89 mm (± 0.87) and females had 26.93 mm (± 0.88), with a highly significant difference ($p=0.00$). At L2, the mean diameters were 30.29 mm (± 0.91) for males and 29.65 mm (± 0.90) for females, showing a sig-

nificant difference ($p=0.03$). L3 showed no significant difference between males (32.20 mm ± 1.18) and females (31.59 mm ± 1.21) with $p=0.11$.

Significant differences were also observed at L4, where males had a mean diameter of 35.35 mm (± 0.85) compared to females at 34.78 mm (± 0.90) with $p=0.04$, and at L5, with males at 37.04 mm (± 0.86) and females at 36.46 mm (± 0.77) with $p=0.03$.

Table 3: Comparison of pedicle length in male and female

Vertebral Dimension	Di- mension	Vertebral level	Male		Female		Paired sam- ple test t-test
			Rt Mean±SD	Lt Mean±SD	Rt Mean±SD	Lt Mean±SD	
Pedicle length		L1	10.65±0.13	10.45±0.14	10.64±0.13	10.42±0.16	0.00**
		L2	10.36±0.12	10.19±0.09	10.3±0.11	10.15±0.10	0.00**
		L3	9.74±0.11	9.55±0.11	9.74±0.15	9.56±0.15	0.00**
		L4	9.36±0.10	9.20±0.07	9.35±0.10	9.21±0.09	0.00**
		L5	8.64±0.16	8.43±0.16	8.63±0.14	8.44±0.16	0.00**

The study analyzed the pedicle length of lumbar vertebrae (L1 to L5) in both male and female subjects, comparing the right and left sides.

Significant differences were found between the right and left pedicle lengths at all levels.

For L1, the right pedicle length in males was 10.65±0.13 mm and the left was 10.45±0.14 mm, while in females the right was 10.64±0.13 mm and the left was 10.42±0.16 mm (p=0.00). Similar sig-

nificant differences were observed for L2 (males: right 10.36±0.12 mm, left 10.19±0.09 mm; females: right 10.3±0.11 mm, left 10.15±0.10 mm), L3 (males: right 9.74±0.11 mm, left 9.55±0.11 mm; females: right 9.74±0.15 mm, left 9.56±0.15 mm), L4 (males: right 9.36±0.10 mm, left 9.20±0.07 mm; females: right 9.35±0.10 mm, left 9.21±0.09 mm), and L5 (males: right 8.64±0.16 mm, left 8.43±0.16 mm; females: right 8.63±0.14 mm, left 8.44±0.16 mm), all with p=0.00.

Table 4: Comparisons of vertebral dimensions between dry bones and MRI at the level of L1

Vertebral level	Vertebral dimensions	t -test
L1(DRY BONE vs MRI)	Vertebral body anteroposterior diameter	0.17
	Vertebral body transverse diameter	0.00**
	spinal canal anteroposterior diameter	0.01*
	spinal canal transverse diameter	0.00**
	pedicle length right side	0.00**
	pedicle length left side	0.00**

The study compared vertebral dimensions of L1 between dry bones and MRI. The analysis revealed no significant difference in the vertebral body anteroposterior diameter (p=0.17). However, significant differences were found in the vertebral body transverse diameter (p=0.00**), spinal canal anteroposterior diameter (p=0.01*), spinal canal transverse diameter (p=0.00**), and pedicle lengths on both the right (p=0.00**) and left sides (p=0.00**).(table 4)

Discussion

Neurological impairments and back instability will occur if a disease affects a major portion of the vertebral body. Internal fixation of the vertebral column is the most effective treatment option for traumatic spine injuries, lumbar canal stenosis, spondylolisthesis, and malignant tumors. Internal fixation provides superior stabilization and reduces the duration of morbidity. Spinal surgery is also conducted for prolapsed intervertebral disc and diseases such as scoliosis.

According to reports, this surgery is considered one of the most difficult to conduct due to its high risk of postoperative complications. [7] Krag et al. [8] conducted a morphometric analysis of cadaver vertebrae using both physical and radiographic methods. By characterizing the shape of the spine in different populations, it would be possible to tailor

the settings in which each individual should be subjected to. The morphometric data of the vertebrae are not only valuable in the domain of neurosurgery, but also indispensable to disciplines such as neurology and orthopedics. The dimensions of the cervical and thoracic spine were previously established in our collections few years ago. [9] This study builds upon previous research and focuses on identifying the characteristics in the lumbar vertebrae. The morphometric data obtained from this study on the different components of lumbar vertebrae can be regarded as the standard data for our study population.

There is a scarcity of studies investigating the morphometry of pars inter-articularis. It provides structural support to the vertebral column and is considered the primary support. The pars inter-articularis is a compact layer of cortical bone that is seen in posterior surgical techniques. Morphometric investigations involve the use of radiological technologies such as radiography and computed tomogram scans. [10]

The robustness of the vertebral column has greatly risen throughout time, which has also affected the size of the vertebral body. [10] Kapoor et al. reported that the inter-pedicular distance measured 18.5 mm at the first lumbar vertebra and 21.5 mm at the lower lumbar vertebrae [11]. Aly and Amin

(2012) [12] documented that the interpedicular distance in the lumbar vertebrae ranges from 17 to 43.4 mm, with a gradual rise towards the lower area. Nayak et al. [13] stated that the diameters of the vertebral foramen are greater in atypical lumbar vertebrae compared to usual ones.

In males, the body of the vertebrae had a height of 171 cm, whereas in females it measured 158.2 cm. [10] During neurosurgery procedures such as pedicle screw insertion, difficulties can arise due to factors such as inadequate implant design, incorrect depth of insertion, variations in bone structure, and mistakes made by the surgeon. These complications may include damage to the meninges, leakage of cerebrospinal fluid, and harm to neurovascular systems. Fourteen having a deep understanding of human anatomy, specifically the measurements and angles of the pedicles in respect to anatomical landmarks that are relevant to clinical practice, can help avert these issues. [14] A research conducted in South Africa examined the racial differences in the bone structure of dried lumbar vertebrae. Fifteen The current study did not investigate racial differences and could not compare with previously published results due to discrepancies in the measurement methods used.

In our study the male has higher anteroposterior diameter of spinal canal at all levels than female, so female has high chance to getting lumbar spinal canal stenosis than male. So our study results are similar to Mohammed Ahamed Abuelnour et al study. Our study deviates from Bukke Ravindra Naik et al study.

In this investigation, we were unable to categorize the vertebrae based on their quantity, age, and gender. Further categorizing the lumbar vertebrae into typical and atypical groups could have enhanced clarity and precision. This can be seen as a constraint of this anatomical investigation. The study did not include an additional observer to assess the repeatability of the measurements. It would have been more advantageous if a portion of the sample had been assessed by a secondary observer and statistical analysis using intra class correlation had been conducted.

Even if the measurements are routinely collected by one observer but are inaccurate, and then averaged to obtain a single result, it may still not accurately represent the actual diameters of the vertebrae. Statistically validating the concurrence between these measurements would enhance the research's robustness. If there is a high level of intra-observer error, it may indicate the need for improved measurement definitions or the use of other techniques in the field of vertebral morphometry.

Due to the nature of the study being a cross-sectional anatomical investigation using dried vertebrae, it was not possible to verify if the specimens

came from the same corpse as they were randomly collected. Further research including a bigger group of participants and the use of established techniques for precise geometric measurements would be beneficial for investigating this intricate anatomical structure. Nevertheless, this study provides information on the pars interarticularis of the lumbar vertebrae, a topic that is rarely discussed in scientific literature. This finding is intriguing since it is unique in the field of anatomy and diverges from earlier studies.

Conclusion

The present research work presents the measurements of specific components of the lumbar vertebrae of individuals from the south Indian population. These findings are expected to assist neurosurgeons and spine surgeons in performing procedures such as laminectomy and decompression. Additionally, they play a crucial role in determining the precise dimensions of the plates and screws used in internal fixation. The implants must be fabricated based on the anatomical dimensions of the specific sample group.

Ethical statement: Institutional ethical committee accepted this study. The study was approved by the institutional human ethics committee, PSG Institute of Medical Science & Research in Coimbatore (Ref No: PSG/HEC/ 2018/Appr/Exp/311 Dated: 27-12-2018).

Authors' contributions: Dr. S. Megala & Dr. B. Paventhan - conceptualization, data curation, investigation, methodology, project administration, visualization, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Dr. Subbulakshmi - conceptualization, methodology, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Dr. G. Amudha - conceptualization, visualization, supervision, writing—original draft. All authors approved the final manuscript as submitted and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Data Availability: All datasets generated or analyzed during this study are included in the manuscript.

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